

KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION AND MANAGEMENT FOR OPERATIONS IN OFFSHORE OIL & GAS IN- DUSTRY: AN APPROACH BASED ON SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

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INTRODUCTION

OVERVIEWS FOR OIL & GAS PRODUCTIONS

In order to produce Oil & Gas (O&G) final products, the O&G production processes will consist three main sequence sectors. The first is upstream, which consists of two sub-sectors are onshore and offshore, is responsible for exploration and production of crude oil and gas from fields to surface facilities for further processing to the pre-treated crude products. The second is midstream which is pertaining to the transportation of the upstream pre-treated crude oil and natural gas to downstream processing plants via transportation facilities. The last is downstream which is responsible for processing the pre-treated crude oil and gas to various domestic products.

The upstream sector is often the most important one in O&G industry because it can bring more profit than the other sectors. The revenue for 2023 of global O&G exploration and production is predicted to be \$2,073,5B (IBIS World, 2023), ranked at the 8th on 10 of Global Biggest Industries. But it is also high risk and complex for management and operations, especially in offshore sector. With harsh environments, the operations of offshore O&G systems always contain higher potential incidents or accidents (Zubaidah, et al, 2016) than onshore production processes. Therefore, the safety and effectiveness in operations are always high challenges for offshore O&G productions (James, 2015).

In O&G operations, a mistake or incoordination can be cause of system failures or even the terrible catastrophes for human life, company assets and environments during operations. For instance, a minor flaw in design of ballast control system

of the offshore Ocean Range platform, which wasn't recognized in time by designers and operators, was cause of platform's sinkage and the dead of 84 operators in 1982 (Canada Royal Commission, 1984). Or the accident of the Deepwater Horizon drilling platform in 2010 at Mexico Gulf was significant case of the inadequate drilling control activities, plus the insufficient training actions for emergency response. The consequences were 11 people dead, platform was collapsed and caused of the largest marine oil spill in the global O&G production history (Bob et al., 2011).

The two disasters had emerged the role of operational knowledge and its management as the important drivers for safety and operational effectiveness during O&G systems' life cycle, as well make the position of standardizations in whole O&G operations.

CONVENTIONAL APPROACH FOR KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITIONS

As a major part of O&G productions, the system operations were including the sequence and logical activities such as observations, supervisions, case studies, evaluations, control and adjustments, diagnostic and making decisions, troubleshooting. The activities were carried out by the skilled operators to keep the systems under safety and performance operations. The operational knowledge which operators need for their activities on the O&G systems will be consisted of:

First, *basic knowledge* related to O&G processes and managements which operational teams would be early trained via educations, training-on-job, case-based studies, simulation trainings.

Second, knowledge about the applicable standards, regulations, procedures, guidelines were required for engineering, operational and managerial activities on the concerned O&G systems. These standards and regulations, e.g. API (2019), DNV (2023), BP (2001) were known as *artifact knowledge or artifacts*, could be issued by government-based organizations or by independent authorities. These artifacts were to ensure the standardizations on O&G operations and kept them under systematic supervisions of companies, national and international authorizers. In order to easy understand by everyone in real world, the artifacts were often presented and stored as descriptive language.

Third, the experienced knowledge as known as *tacit knowledge*, was often acquired in forms of know-how, know-what, know-who from expertized operators and used for site diagnostic, and making decision during operations.

All above knowledge could be acquired via learning or experience (BS ISO 30401, 2018); Or discovered from data and information or from a synthesis of prior knowledge (Irma et al, 2015). The conventional knowledge acquisition (KA) and management (KM) framework could be outlined in Fig 1.

or “null knowledge” was recognized, a validated and consolidated activities would be triggered.

PROBLEM STATEMENTS

The basic knowledge can be acquired via educations and advance trainings. Therefore, it can be absorbed by operators having good background.

For artifact knowledge, the amounts of artifacts may be thousand for each domain. The artifacts are very diversified, multiform, and high specific. Therefore, in-depth understandings, right acquisitions and correct applications of the artifacts for practice become the high challenges for O&G operators.

Regarding to tacit knowledge, it is very useful for quick problem-solving, diagnostic and decision making during operations. However, the type of knowledge is often tacitness, uncodified, wrong or fuzzy meaning especially when some experts are bias or prejudice. Therefore, in practice its applications are often carried out after the knowledge validations and verifications by authorized experts (Hai et al, 2003).

In general, with the vast amount of artifacts and the natural tacit characteristics of human knowledge, the knowledge-based activities will be effectively and smoothly only when the human experts still work in or with operational teams. On the other hand, the human experts are always center of the conventional KA. They also act as examiners to find out and consolidate the outdated or incorrect artifact knowledge in whole project’s life cycle. Therefore, *the first problem for conventional KA and KM is it always rely on human experts for acquiring, verifying, and handling knowledge.*

The second issue is caused by the long life cycle of O&G projects which is often last tens of years and consists of various phases with participations of many manufacturers, logistic providers, operators from many sections. It is absolutely sure an experienced operator cannot work in 20 years of systems’ life cycle and also can’t acquire fully knowledge from such multi-sections. Hence, *knowledge can miss or can’t be transferred fully in the systems’ life cycle.*

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

So far, the research objects are the offshore O&G systems and their operations. The “O&G systems” are the combination of various sub-systems and elements complied with complex social – technical relationships, which need various comprehensive knowledge to operate. And the research problems are how to solve the insufficiencies of the conventional KA and KM. While O&G operational practices, the using of wrong, misunderstanding or outdated and invalid knowledge

can be cause of disasters. Therefore, the serious and real problems stated above had raised two critical questions for the KA and KM:

1. *How to acquire and manage knowledge in some ways that can mitigate the relying on human experts, but still easily to validate, handle the knowledge?*
2. *How to acquire and manage knowledge systematically and doesn't lose or miss in whole O&G project's life cycle?*

LITERATURE REVIEW

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT TRENDS

Recently, the researches on knowledge and KMs had been standardized by some international standards. The knowledge was defined as human or organizational asset that could trigger the effective decisions and actions in specific contexts and conditions. The KM was defined as the management related to knowledge that applied the systemic approaches for improvement of results and learning (BS ISO 30401, 2018). An interaction between a human expert and a knowledge engineer was probably the most common form of KA (Stephen, 2001).

The KM consisted of main processes: creation, analysis, sharing, transferring and applications of knowledge to create companies' value. In practice, the trends of KM often focused on the relationships between KM's main processes with management factors, e.g. new product development (Hans, 2015); innovation performance (Armando et al, 2017); firm competitiveness (James, 2018). Most of these studies were quantitative researches with various mediated variables and dependent constructs.

In O&G industry, only one KM study related to operational service providers was conducted by Jayachandra B. in 2013 which was focused on the human interactions to acquire operational knowledge from existing operational manpower.

In computer-science and Artificial Intelligent (AI), since 1960 the trends of research and applications of computer-aids knowledge-based systems such as expert systems (ESs), machine learning... had been studied and applied for empirical applications (Chuleeporn et al., 2004). The ESs had been studied and developed strongly during last 40 years. ESs deal with mathematical models to describe knowledge as well as developments of reasoning strategies and inference mechanism to proceed knowledge which was acquired from human experts (Thuy, 1999; William, 2005).

SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

In general, Systems Engineering was scientific domain to deal with systems. It was found in the year 1970, as known as Process Systems Engineering (PSE). The initial PSE had focused on using computational techniques for mathematical modelling, simulations, process optimizations in chemical, physics or biology engineering systems. In the end of 2010 the definition of “system” had been expanded to cover both technical and social - management system(s) (NASA, 2007). Systems Engineering had been also expanded its scopes to various industrial systems and known as Industrial Systems Engineering.

At HCMC University of Technology (Vietnam), Systems Engineering had been further developed and consolidated by a new approach methodology which was named System Approach Methodology (SAM) by Hai LX. and Hai VV. (2005, 2017).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For problem-solving on such complex systems, the System Approach Methodology (SAM) of Systems Engineering should be applied. The knowledge acquisition shall be carried out systematically based on the systems’ models, basic knowledge and experts’ supports as outlined in Figure 2.

Figure 2. System-based Knowledge Acquisition Framework

In general, the SAM provides the overall and systematic methods, flow charts, tasks... to study, analyze, evaluate, optimize, and perform necessary tasks to achieve specific targets on any systems (Hai, 2005 and 2017). The complex systems will be disintegrated to smaller and simpler sub-systems and elements until they can be handled, monitored and managed for specific purposes. The data and relationships about the real systems will be discovered and captured from the disintegration. Then the data and relationships will be re-integrated and structured in forms of knowledge to solve the concerned purposes (Hai, 2013). It is different from conventional approach, in SAM framework, *the object(s) of KA process shall be the real system(s) from which knowledge will be created or acquired at specific context(s) and real conditions* (Hai, 2005).

The SAM will imitate the self-learning of human to acquire knowledge about specific system(s). Firstly, the human will approach the concerned system(s). Based on his basic knowledge (1-1) and understandings about system's models (1-2), he will analyze system and identify the system's elements in conjunction with the relationships inside and outside of the system(s). As a knowledge creator, he will summarize, and create operational knowledge for himself in various forms such as experiences, artifacts, lessons learned. During the system approach, the support

facilities (1-3) such as computer-aids search engines, database from similar or relevant systems... will be utilized for in-depth understanding and big data management. The human experts still remain their roles as informants or respondents to provide advance social-technical knowledge. As result, the acquired knowledge base can be directly linked with the real systems or the systems' models, therefore the trustworthiness of the acquired knowledge would be validated, consolidated and updated continuously in whole systems' life cycle. The KM researchers still remain their roles as instruments to analyze, structure and hierarchize the systems' knowledge.

With the SAM, the KA/KM will become team-working processes with participations from multi-discipline experts. From all view angles, the systems' elements will be identified completed with relationships related to the operational requirements. These relationships will be built based on systems' mathematical, physical and managerial constrains on which the real systems are being constructed, hence the bias and prejudice from personnel during knowledge acquisition can be defined and eliminated.

For instance, regarding to operation of a ballast system, which was cause of Ocean Range disaster, the knowledge acquisition for operations won't implemented only via experts' interviews. With SAM's framework, the ballast control system's elements will be identified consisted of ballast sensors, ballast pumps, piping and ballast room... Next, the design for ballast system will be reviewed based on the mass balance mathematical model of platform; then completed with hazardous operations assessment to identify all potential risks can occur so that there isn't single fail of elements can cause of the system failure. As result, the knowledge for operations of the ballast system can be transferred to operators with all operational elements and the social – technical relationships which need for operations, validations, maintenances, emergency response plan... during its operational life cycle.

CURRENT FINDINGS

GENERIC QUALITATIVE APPROACH AND EMPIRICAL APPLICATION

In 2003, the framework in Fig. 1 had been applied to acquire operational knowledge for a computer-based expert system called Cooler ES by Hai VV. and his colleagues (Hai et al, 2003). The Cooler ES had been used for decision making supports during operation of Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioner (HVAC) Systems on offshore platforms in Viet Nam.

To acquire operational knowledge base for the Cooler, a basic qualitative approach had been applied for sampling, testing, and codifying knowledge. A group of HVAC operational experts from company had been interviewed to provide list

of real operational situations of system; how to identify and verify operational contexts; how to check extra conditions and what decision should be made to fix abnormal situations. The expert knowledge was described in form of natural technical language, then was coded by mathematical statement logic to be processed by computer. Based on AI techniques, the Cooler ES could interact with operators via question and answer interfaces, then performed some AI's reasoning strategies to support operators for diagnostic and making decision.

The Cooler ES had been approved for application in company. However, some disadvantages from the conventional KA approach were recognized as follow:

- It was relied on human experts and their experiences, and especial difficult to acquire knowledge from experts when they weren't always willingness to share their knowledge. When experts left the companies, their knowledge was unable to revise, update, verify and consolidate any more.
- The experts' differential views could be cause of argument on the acquired knowledge. And the acquired knowledge might be wrong, not codified or bias, hence lead to difficult in knowledge validations, verifications and applications.
- Errors could occur during knowledge creation by human expert or during acquisition by knowledge engineer. But knowledge engineers couldn't define and recognize the wrongs and inconsistencies of the acquired knowledge. As result, it was difficult and taken a lot of time to validate the acquired knowledge prior to apply for practice.

The disadvantages of the conventional KA for Cooler ES in practice had limited its developments and emerged the necessity of a consolidated approach for the ES development.

SYSTEM-BASED APPROACH FOR HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (HMR)

HMR was also the critical concerns for new and important industries. In 2010, with plan to build two nuclear power plants (NPP) 1000MW at Viet Nam, the HRM had been raised because the local operational workforces might be not available. The required manpower for operations of the NPPs 1000MW was proposed by IAEA to be 1000 persons ((IAEA, 2007). But an empirical open questions were how many manpower with specific disciplines and at specific educational degrees would be required to operate these power plants.

Based on framework in Fig 2, in 2013 at AIT, a HMR research had been carried out to answer the above open question (Hai, 2013). The study had found out the total of manpower required for the first NPP was 1017 staffs with all levels from superintendents to craftsmen. In which the post-graduate degree was 66 persons;

the undergraduate staffs for all sections were 151, and 800 skilled technicians would be required for operational activities. The study had also proposed plan and schedule for national educational and training programs to develop and manage the HR for the NPPs.

RESEARCH PLAN AND IMPLICATIONS

First, a general research for knowledge acquisition methodology shall be carried out, and applied for a case study on the Control Systems of O&G production platforms. The Control Systems are one of the most important systems while all control and operational activities will be implemented via the systems. The Control Systems' operations require the high comprehensive knowledge about process, mechanic, automation engineering, computer science... as well must be complied with stringent standards and regulations as known as artifacts. Therefore, a multi-discipline knowledge acquisition for operations of the Control Systems will be conducted based on framework Fig 2 of SAM.

Second, in order to consolidate AI applications which are based on tacit knowledge, the ES Cooler will be upgraded based on the SAM framework, and applied for decision making activities in control and operation of O&G platform. Learning from the previous study, the system-based approach will consolidate and fix the disadvantages of the conventional knowledge acquisition. The tacitness from human experts' experiences and knowledge will be explicated based on mathematical – physical relationships of O&G systems.

For practical implications, the research is predicted to provide the consolidations for conventional KA and KM with overall outcomes as follow:

First, the acquired knowledge about system will be acquired systematically in conjunction with the system's mathematical, physical and managerial models. It allows operators to deeply understand the complex knowledge as well provide the basis to validate and explain the acquired knowledge, especially know-how experiences. The criterion will ensure the correction and tangibility of knowledge. It will be also a basis to evaluate the trustworthiness of the acquired knowledge for knowledge sharing and transformation.

Second, the knowledge about systems will be acquired according to standardized flow charts, frameworks and methodologies of Systems Engineering which will be developed, handled and applied for whole life cycle of Oil & Gas production systems. As consequence, all operators in operational phase will able know what, when, where knowledge created, acquired, applied for specific targets at specific contexts in any phase of the O&G project.

For social and managerial implications, the research will propose a systemized approach for the KM and its applications in organizations:

First, it will allow operators to understand and manage the hierarchy of the acquired knowledge in relevant with the real systems. The criterion will ensure the depth understanding for contexts, conditions and limitations that knowledge created or acquired.

Second, with SAM, the operational activities will be studied, approached step-by-step from general systems to all levels of sub-systems, components, elements in conjunction with their relationships according with engineering and social standards and regulations.

And third, beside the applications for knowledge management, SAM will be able referred and applied for manpower administrations, decision making in psychology and operations research as well the optimizations in operations...

In conclusion, SAM framework can be seen as combination between the generic qualitative approach with Systems Engineering techniques. With a combined approach, the research will provide not only a basic qualitative approach but also specific methodology for studies on the complex systems. Therefore, the research will be able expanded to other system issues such as risk managements, scheduling and planning, data and resource managements... for other industries and management requirements.

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